

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNAL SUPERVISION OF THE IN-IN-OUT PROGRAMME IN THE COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN THE WESTERN REGIONS OF GHANA

Jerry Isaac Ortsin¹,
Ebenezer Appah Bonney¹ⁱ,
Derrick Kwesi Ntsiful¹,
Genevieve Huedenu¹
Bliss Cornelius Sedega²

¹Holy Child College of Education,
Takoradi, Ghana

²Akatsi College of Education,
Ghana

Abstract:

The study was aimed at finding out the effectiveness of internal supervision of the In-In-Out programme in the Colleges of Education in the Western Region of Ghana. The purpose of the study was to find out problems facing supervision of the In-In-Out programme. The research design for the study is the descriptive survey. This method permitted the researchers to obtain data to determine specific characteristics of the group. In all, 480 respondents were included in the study, which comprised 300 Mentees, 180 Mentors. The instrument used in collecting the data was a questionnaire. Data analysis was mainly descriptive. The study revealed that all the supervisors had a problem with non-payment of allowance for supervision. In addition, the supervisors and mentees hardly used teaching and learning materials during the teaching-learning process. Some of the supervisors did not perform their expected roles. It is recommended that the Teacher Education Division of the Ghana Education Service should provide the supervisors with attractive allowances to enable them to supervise the mentees teaching effectively. Again, the Principals in the Colleges of Education should increase the period for the training of the mentors so that they would acquire all the necessary skills for effective supervision.

Keywords: internal supervision, in- in-out programme, colleges of education, Ghana

¹ Correspondence: email bonney2007@yahoo.co.uk

1. Introduction

No matter one's starting point, the evidence is that the educational system all over the world is undergoing change. Public demand for improvement in the quality of education is the continuous reform of the curriculum, particularly the organization of teaching and learning experiences.

According to Antwi (1992), education refers to an organized and sustained instruction designed to communicate a combination of knowledge, skills and understanding valuable for all the activities in life. This means education is the acquisition of skills, attitudes and knowledge which enables a person to fit into a society. Education, therefore, is critical in nation-building. The quality of teachers in our schools and the quality of Teacher Education (TED) in Ghana are inseparable (Adentwi, 2002).

Teacher education in Ghana dates as far back as pre-independence era. The Teacher Education Division of the Ghana Education Service is in charge of Teacher Education Programmes. It is tasked with the pre-service and in-service training of teachers. The aim of the division is to train quality teachers to teach in our schools at the basic education level to promote better learning outcomes.

Adentwi (2002) attested that teacher education in Ghana has undergone several structural and content changes from a 4-year certificate. Prior to 1951, there were 19 pre-university Training Colleges leading to the award of:

- Two-Year Post-Middle Teachers Certificate 'B';
- Two-Year Post 'B' teachers certificate 'A';
- Four-Year Post-Middle Teachers Certificate 'A';
- Two-Year Post-Secondary Teachers Certificate 'A'.

Criticisms of teachers' performance in education necessitated an overview of teacher preparation in Ghana. Basically, teacher education follows these procedures: Academic and Professional preparation; observation, micro-teaching, peer-group teaching and off-campus teaching practice (Adentwi, 2002).

Trainees took an academic upgrading and updating course in the first year and pursued a vigorous course in curriculum studies integrated with the methodology in the second year. In addition to a component of the methodology course, trainees were given a series of demonstration lessons and they did the prescribed periods of campus-based practice teaching. Tamakloe (1997), on his part, viewed the purpose of practice teaching generally to be to provide opportunities for student teachers to develop and evaluate their competencies in the major areas of teaching.

According to Adentwi (2002), this practice was very complex since College administrators made all arrangements and logistics ready before trainees could go to their allocated schools in the communities for syllabuses. They collected other materials and prepared schemes of work, prepared the weekly forecast and lesson notes as well as teaching and learning materials. Trainees moved from campus to the schools to practice. Tutors on campus vetted the lesson notes. The class teachers hardly played any role. From time to time tutors went to supervise trainee's teaching. They went with

Assessment Forms, observed and rated trainees while they taught. By the time this exercise was over, teacher trainees might have been supervised only three times or at best five for the four weeks.

Adentwi (2002) identifies two important weaknesses of teaching practice assessment in the then training colleges. In the first place, teaching practice did not ensure that trainees reflected on their teaching experiences in order to build upon their strong points and remedy any short-coming. This also points out that reflection in practice should include the trainees so as to encourage them to think about the practice by self-evaluation.

The challenges that faced trainees in the former practice centred on the vetting of notes by tutors who performed the dual roles of vetting their notes as well as supervising teaching. Most often, trainees collected the vetted notes late or in the morning before going to practice. If notes had to be re-written or corrected or teaching-learning material (TLM) was to be made the trainees became frustrated and would not know what to do. (Adentwi, 2002)

The movement from college campuses to schools of practice prevented the trainees from experiencing the realities of teaching. They could not take part in most co-curricular activities in schools. Trainees did not have enough time to mark assignments let alone exercises given in class because they were commuting between the college and the schools. They had little interaction with the pupils and the teachers in the schools. They had no interaction with the parents of the children they were teaching.

With the various strategies adopted by the Ghana government to attain short-term basic education for all children of school going-age by the year 2015 and achieving the subsequent long-term vision of becoming a middle-income country, education, in general, has been revised (MOE, 1996). Teacher education curriculum, which is the epicentre of quality education, was revised to provide well-qualified teachers for the basic schools, hence the launching of the In-In-Out Programme of initial training in 1998/1999 academic year as part of the FCUBE Programme.

The In-In-Out Programme is an innovation in the then Teacher Training College programme established to move away from the academic orientation of teacher training to the situation where performance is based on practical teaching.

Some of the innovative activities include;

- a) Whole year school focused system of practical training of teacher trainees.
- b) The use of distance education methodology as a mode of instruction and study and
- c) The employment of mentors to work with link tutors for the supervision of teacher trainees.

According to Atta and Baafi (2000), organizational structure refers to the way in which organizations are divided, organized and coordinated. It provides stability and keeps the organization's members together to achieve set goals. Based on the importance of organizational structure to organizations, the teacher education division is made-up of;

- a) The director of the Teacher Education Division and the core staff members (the management);
- b) Principles of Teacher Training Colleges (the implementers);
- c) Tutors of Teacher Training Colleges (External Supervisors/Link Tutors);
- d) The Basic School headteachers (Internal Supervisors/Mentors);
- e) Basic School heads/teachers (Internal supervision);
- f) Teacher trainees (mentees on off-campus teaching practices);

The goal of this new programme is to produce qualified and effective teachers for basic schools through competency-based training, which is integrated with the teaching of theory and performance in the classroom.

According to the Ghana Education Service (GES), the implementation of the In-In-Out programme is directed by the following principles;

- a) Teacher trainees should be regarded as students in training and not as qualified teachers.
- b) The teacher-trainees are to teach not more than four periods a day to allow them to have sufficient time for personal study.
- c) Teacher trainees should be given adequate supervision and guidance as they teach in order to allow them to develop professional skills expected of a professionally qualified teacher.
- d) The work study aspect of the Teacher Training Programme (TTP) which is offered to teacher trainees in the third year should be regarded as part of the three year teacher training programme.

The teacher training programme is of three years duration. Teacher trainees will spend the first two years on the College campus and will be taught using the conventional face-to-face methods. In the first year, trainees are taught academic courses in the subjects taught at the basic level. During the second year, curriculum studies integrated with methodology (demonstration lessons and campus-based practice teaching) courses are offered.

One year attachment programme, where trainees stay in communities of the practicing schools other than that of their colleges is organized. They undertake school-based training. That is, apart from practice teaching, they are also exposed to practical issues such as school management, discipline among staff and other relations and communal living. The attachment programme includes membership training and supervision (Ghana National Association of Teachers, 2003). The teacher trainees are expected to go through a programmed course while on attachment. They are supplied with distance learning materials which cover all the fourteen subjects taught at the basic education level. The additional materials are devoted to education studies. Other resource materials like lesson notebooks are also provided for teacher trainees.

It is anticipated that teacher trainees should have study cycle in order to discuss issues on proficiency and school community-based programme which they will be examined on at the end of their final year as well as writing their project work. They are expected to be involved in community activities.

The trainees are accommodated in groups in their various communities. They prepare to teach, prepare lesson notes and deliver lessons, give and mark exercises and are involved in all co-curricular activities of the school. They are expected to be regular and punctual at school, exhibit acceptable personality traits and develop a good interpersonal relationship with other mentees, staff and people of the community. The introduction of the "In-In-Out programme has provided a whole academic year of attachment to schools to provide sufficient time for teacher trainees to practice teaching and become competent in teaching. This enables them to benefit from performance as a critical method for acquiring competent teacher status.

It has also provided familiarization of village life to some of the teacher trainees who may not have stayed in a village before. This programme puts strong links between the College's schools and communities where trainees are attached for mutual benefits. The activities of the "In-In-Out" programme and its benefits can be sustained and improved if there is effective supervision. Hamily (1987) stated in his book "Assessing the Abilities and Instructional Needs of Students" that supervision helps teachers to learn whether or not the prescribed intervention has been beneficial.

Tamakloe (1997), in evaluating the National Conference of Teacher Education held in 1986, formulated that the present one-way communication nature of the post-observation conference must give way to a two-way communication between the student-teacher and the supervisor. How the mentors are able to adhere to Tamakloe's evaluation is a test case for teacher education. Also, how the mentors are able to supervise both co-curricular and intra-curricular activities are the greatest concern of this research. This has prompted the researchers to undertake this study in order to find out the effectiveness of internal supervision of the "In-In-Out" programme in Colleges of Education in the Western Region.

2. Statement of the Problem

The most important task of supervisors, as far as teaching is concerned, is to stimulate students to evaluate their own teaching by making their supervision clinical. Stones (1984) stated that, ideally, the teaching practice supervision exercise is to build up the confidence level of the teacher trainees and help develop their professional skills. In view of the fact that the internship programme is an evolving scheme of training teachers in Ghana and that most of such schemes require effective supervision and monitoring; this study seeks to investigate whether the internal supervision of the "In-In-Out" programme in the Colleges of Education in the Western Region is effective and what its impact is on the teaching and learning process.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to find out the effectiveness of internal supervision, which is being practiced in the In-In-Out programme in the Colleges of Education in the Western Region of Ghana and its impact on the teaching and learning process.

2.2 Research Questions

The following research questions have been formulated to guide and direct investigation.

1. What training do supervisors acquire?
2. How effective do supervisors play their roles?
3. What problems do supervisors face during supervision?
4. What problems do mentees face in so far as internal supervision is concerned?
5. In what ways could the problems be solved?

3. Research Design

The research design for this study is the descriptive survey. The design deals with assessing the effectiveness of internal supervision of the “In-In-Out” programme in the Colleges of Education in the Western Region of Ghana. This method permitted the researchers to obtain data to determine specific characteristics of the group. The descriptive survey design enables the researchers to use observation and questionnaire, which represented the most appropriate method for conducting the investigation. It was appropriate to use this method for this research because it had the potential to provide a lot of information from quite a large sample of individuals and enabled the researchers to make an inference and generalization on findings from the study (Best and Khaln, 1995).

3.1 Population

The study investigated the effectiveness of internal supervision of the “In-In-Out” programme in the Colleges of Education in the Western Region of Ghana that is, Holy Child College of Education, Wiawso College of Education and Enchi College of Education. The population consisted of mentees in the three Colleges of Education in the named region. The mentors came from the basic schools in the catchment area within the Western Region where the mentees do their teaching practice. The total population for the study was 1059 persons made up of 601 mentees, 458 mentors.

3.2 Sampling

A sample of 300 mentees, that is, 100 each from the three colleges, and 180 mentors, that is, 60 from each college were used in the study making a total of 480.

In selecting the student’s respondents from the population of the final year trainees on attachment in the three Colleges of Education, a stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting mentees from each of the two mixed Teacher Colleges of Education and a simple random sampling technique was used for the single-sex Teacher Colleges of Education in the Western Region.

A list of mentees was obtained from each of the Colleges of Education by the researchers. The names obtained were listed according to sex for the two mixed Colleges of Education. The numbers were written on pieces of paper, folded and put in a box and the pieces of paper were randomly picked from the box. The mentees whose

names matched the numbers made up the sample. In the mixed Colleges of Education, that is, Enchi and Wiawso the 100 mentees selected were made up of 70 males and 30 females.

The mentors were purposively selected because they were few and all of them play key roles in the programme. Patton (1990) explained that purposive sampling is based on the assumption that the investigator wants to discover, understand and gain insight and therefore must select a sample from which the most can be learned.

3.3 Instrumentation

To enable the respondents to supply the needed data on the study, the researchers used a questionnaire and observation for the mentees and mentors. These instruments are known for their validity and reliability. The researchers constructed the instruments based on the literature review and research questions because self-developed instruments are known for their appropriateness for the design and information retrieval. The questionnaire was used because it enabled the researchers to collect data from the mentees and mentors in the activities of internal supervision of the “In-In-Out” programme.

The questionnaire designed for the mentors consisted mostly of Likert scale type, close-ended items (where respondents were given options from which they were to select what responses they deemed appropriate) and a few open-ended items where the respondents had to provide their own responses.

3.4 Observation Process

The researchers also employed observation on some major issues of the programme for the triangulation process. Specifically, the researchers used non-participant observation. The non-participant observation is one of the ways used to see what is going on in a given social setting. The researchers were physically present but only as a spectator who does not become directly involved in the activities of people who are being studied. Observation process is a major means of collecting data in both qualitative and quantitative research. It offers a first-hand account of the situation under study (Agyedu and Donkor, 1999).

The researchers prepared an outline for the observation process. It was made up of the content of training for mentors, mentors’ involvement in pre-conference meeting, mentors’ involvement in classroom activities, mentors’ involvement in post-conference activities and appropriate use of teaching and learning materials. The observation was carried out for three weeks during the mentee’s internship in some selected places of attachment. Issues that required additional evidence through observation provided the frame for the schedule.

3.5 Pre-Testing of Instruments

Since the research instrument was personally designed, there was the need to check the reliability and validity of the questionnaire and observation schedule used for final data collection. There was the need to find out if items contained in the instruments were

explicit enough and would, therefore, aid the respondents to complete the questionnaire as accurately as possible and whether the observation process would bring out the expected behavior from mentees.

The process of the study helped the researchers to detect inherent problems, inconsistencies and ambiguities in the instruments intended to be used for the study and corrected such abnormalities before carrying out the actual study (Fraenkel & Wallen, 1993). The sample for the pre-test was 45 respondents. They were selected from Essaman Primary and JHS, Kissi D/A Primary, Kissi D/A JHS, Kissi English and Arabic Primary and Kissi English and Arabic JHS all in the catchment area of Komenda College of Education. The breakdown was 30 mentees and 15 mentors.

The pre-testing was done in two weeks before the actual study to make room for corrections. The study was conducted when the basic schools were in their last part of the second term so that the mentees would have had some experience in the programme to validate the content of the instruments used. It was subjected to the experts in the college for scrutiny and comment. The researchers collected all the questionnaires administered and ran the responses using (Cronbach's alpha coefficient) for the reliability coefficient. After the reliability test has been run the result was 0.75. This outcome proved that the instrument used was valid and reliable.

In spite of this test using the computer software, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), further adjustments were made to the instruments for easy administration. As a result of the corrections made some items were revised for clarity while some others were eliminated or regrouped. These processes were in line with Agyedu and Donkor (1999) contention that "*reliability and validity of documents and personal accounts can be assessed through various techniques and triangulations.*"

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaires were personally administered by the researchers. The respondents were briefed on the objectives of the study and assured of their anonymity and confidentiality. The names and schools of the respondents were optional. These helped to solicit the needed support and co-operation of the respondents to ensure that the work was successfully done.

Looking at the magnitude of work and time limit for the exercise, respondents were grouped and briefed on the purpose of the study. After that, the questionnaires were distributed to respondents who filled them and returned some few hours afterward on the same day. This ensured a 100% return rate. The writers also personally observed a few mentors in the mentoring, a few mentees in teaching and a few mentees in their involvement in school worship. The writers also visited some of their places of abode and interacted with them. The observation helped to cross-check what they said on the items. The administration of the questionnaires for mentors and mentees took one week each. The observation took two weeks.

3.7 Data Analysis

The data were qualitatively and quantitatively analysed. Some set of data were analysed using frequency tables and in some cases making the presentation of data in prose because the items could not be presented in tabular forms. To be precise, quantitative analysis was made using simple descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages.

The responses were edited and analysed according to specific research questions. The closed-ended items were coded and fed into the computer using software, Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS). This software is useful in much respect because it helps to run frequencies, percentages, draw tables, charts and bars.

4. Results and Discussions

Research question one: What is the background training of internal supervisors?

The background training of the respondents has been presented in Table 1

Table 1: Duration of the training of mentors

Duration of training	Frequency	Percentage
One day	107	59.4
One week	57	31.7
Two weeks	7	3.9
Three weeks	9	5
Total	180	100

On the duration of training of internal supervisors, it was found that majority of the mentors representing 59.4% indicated that they had one day training session. The mentors were to be taken through types of supervision, characteristics of supervision, beliefs of supervision, theories of supervision and functions of supervision, mentoring process among others. Anderson and Shawmon (1998) stated that the mentoring process has five essential attributes namely, the process of nurturing, the act of serving as a role model, mentoring section and caring relationship. The above assertion shows that an in-depth training is needed to be provided for mentors to make them capable of giving adequate needed help to mentees.

It is quite clear that the one-day training session was woefully inadequate if the components of supervision which the mentors should know are taken into consideration. There is the likelihood that their mentoring activities will be adversely affected. Consequently, the teacher trainees will not be able to acquire the skills they need for effective teaching and learning.

On the content of training, the mentors were taken through information on how to prepare lesson notes, the use of distance learning materials and how to supervise, as well as mentors relationship with teacher trainees.

Table 2: Effectiveness of Training for mentors

Effective training	Frequency	Percentage
Very effective	4	2.2
Effective	52	28.9
Not effective	124	68.9
Total	180	100

Sixty-eight point nine percent (68.9%) of the mentors indicated that the training they had was not effective. The results of the study show that training for the mentors on the internal supervision of the In-In-Out programme was not effective and this could affect the performance of the mentors when mentoring the students. Harris (1963) was of the view that instructional supervision is carried out by selecting and assigning the appropriate instructions to staff members in the organization. This can only be achieved through effective training. Periodic in-service training is important for all sections of teachers and has to be organized as such. These mentors are performing supervisory roles in the training of teachers so constant training in supervision cannot be overemphasized. Neagley and Evans (1970) suggested that supervisory activities should be included in in-service programmes to upgrade the knowledge of personnel for effective supervision.

Research questions two: How effective do the supervisors play their mentoring roles?

This research question sought to find out effective roles played by supervisors (mentors) in the “In-In-Out programme of initial Colleges of Education in the Western Region of Ghana. The areas considered were on pre-conference and post-conference meetings as well as the supervisor’s participation in co-curricular activities. The responses given by mentors under this research question are presented in prose with subheadings.

Table 3: Mentees’ teaching, pre-conference meeting with mentees and participation in co-curricular activities

Item	Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Do you have pre-conference meeting with mentees	178	98.9	2	1.1
Do you stay in the classroom during mentee's teaching activities?	100	55.6	80	44.4
Do you participate in co-curricular activities with mentees	15	8.3	165	91.7

The mentors do pre-conference meetings with the teacher trainees before teaching. This was confirmed by 98.9% of the respondents. Pre-conference meeting is a pre-requisite for a smooth mentoring process. During this meeting, the mentors brief the teacher trainees on how they can go about their teaching. They also find out how prepared the mentees are and guide them as to the types of pedagogies to use for the lesson.

In spite of the fact that most of the mentors indicated they do have pre-conference meetings with mentees, it has been observed that some mentors only wet the lesson notes of the mentees. This actually contradicts what Tamakloe (1997) stressed

regarding pre-conference meetings. He said pre-conference meeting is needed to guide mentees in their lesson notes preparation, selection of teaching and learning materials, instilling confidence and giving pep talks on good classroom management. Also, Neagley and Evans (1970) said the primary role of supervisors is to have a discussion with the mentees before going into the classroom and the discussions should focus on;

- a) Making organizational arrangement to implement the curriculum.
- b) Selecting and assigning the appropriate instructional material for teaching and learning.
- c) Instilling confidence into the teacher.

Again, it was observed that 55.6% of the mentors stayed in the classroom whilst mentees taught. It is a good practice for all the mentors to stay in the classrooms as the mentees teach. Supervisors are responsible for working with mentees to increase the effectiveness of teaching and learning in the schools. When they are in the class, they can guide the mentees better. This situation by all standards is in the right direction and it is buttressed by what Musaazi (1982) stated.

On the other hand, it was found that only 44.4 percent of the mentors did not stay in the classroom during lessons delivery. Most mentors leave their classrooms for the mentees to do their own things. One of the reasons for the mentors gave for not staying in their classrooms throughout the mentees' lessons was that, they went to the bank for their salaries and others said they were sick. This implies that once they are not in the classroom, they cannot effectively guide the mentees. The uncooperative attitude of a section of the mentors is in contradiction of what Tamakloe (1997) stated that classroom should not be on holiday during teaching practice rather they should always be available to give guidance to the mentees.

Mentors are to participate in co-curricular activities to supervise the mentees. It was observed that 91.7% of the mentors did not participate in co-curricular activities. However, the remaining 8.3% of the mentors participated in co-curricular activities. The results of the study indicate that most mentors do not participate in co-curricular activities with mentees.

It is the responsibility of the mentors to take an active part in co-curricular activities so that they can supervise the mentees during that period. Although mentees take part in co-curricular activities, they were not given any guidance; rather they were left on their own. Mentees were left to lead devotions and assemblies, supervise pupils during cleaning of the compound and more are left to conduct some of these activities, but the room is, supervisors should be on hand to correct deviation that may crop up along the line (Derrick and Dicks, 2005).

The failure of the mentors to participate in co-curricular activities implies that they are not fulfilling some of the responsibility. Aseidu - Akrofi (1978) stated that the supervisor's role is to work cooperatively with the mentee to create avoidable circumstances that may inhibit teaching and learning in schools. This can be done through such co-curricular activities like sports, entertainment and so on. The mentors have an important role to play in the training of mentees and any negligence on the part should not be countenanced (Gadzirayi, Muropa and Mutandwa, 1999).

Research questions three: What problems do supervisors (mentors) face during supervision of mentees?

The research sought to find out what problems supervisors (mentors) face during the supervisory process. This section of the study looked at the allowance for supervisors and teaching and learning materials.

All the respondents responded that they are not given any allowance for supervising the trainees either in cash or any other form. The non-payment of allowance to the supervisors mean that they are not motivated in any way and as a result, the college authorities should not expect to get the full cooperation of mentors. According to Asamoah (2001) motivation enables the teacher to secure the attention and participation of his class in his lessons. It maintains discipline and enhances responsibility. He made this assertion with regard to the classroom teacher and his or her pupils but is still valid in this instance because internal supervisors are supposed to play an important role in the programme of training teachers but they do not receive any form of remuneration. These states of affairs explain the non-participation of mentors in co-curricular activities of their respective schools leaving mentees to their fate.

Table 4 shows the responses on the teaching and learning materials mentors and mentees use during teaching.

Table 4: Teaching and learning materials mentors and mentees use during teaching

Teaching	Mentors		Mentees	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Textbooks	64	35.6	91	30.3
Pictures	103	57.2	198	66
Improved materials	15	8.3	11	3.7
Total	180	100	300	100

Table 9 shows that 57.2% of the mentors and 66.0% of the mentees used only pictures to teach the pupils. Also, 35.6% of the mentors and 30.3% of the mentees respectively used textbooks to teach the pupils. This implies that pictures and textbooks were the teaching-learning materials that were available in the schools of attachment. These responses show that there is a problem regarding the use of teaching and learning materials in the school system. Indeed it is a problem and it is not insurmountable because most of the teaching and learning materials could be made by teachers but they claimed they are not motivated and unmotivated teachers are not expected to sacrifice especially where it has to deal with money.

A Chinese maxim states "I hear and I forget, I see and I remember and I do and I understand". All that this maxim means is that when pupils are taught with audio-visual aids the understanding is great. Teaching and learning materials are always needed for delivery lessons in the classroom and their availability is very crucial more especially during training sessions (Gadzirayi, Muropa & Mutandwa, 1999).

The mentees' responses on how often the mentees use teaching and learning materials have been presented in Table 5.

Table 5: How often do you use teaching and learning materials?

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Most often	83	27.7
Always	118	39.3
Often	99	33
Total	300	100

The benefits that are derived from teaching and learning materials (TLMs) are enormous in teaching and learning process. Therefore, mentees who are still under training cannot teach without using them. Table 5 shows that they always used TLMs during lessons in the classroom. The responses of mentees are supported by what Asamoah (2001) suggested regarding the use of TLMs. He outlined that TLMs are useful because they help pupils to participate fully in lessons; they equip the mentees for the job that pupils become interested in the subjected being taught.

During observation, it was found that mentees used TLMs when they realized that an external supervisor was coming to the school to supervise them. They did not use the TLMs as often as they claimed. The reason they gave was that there was a lack of funds to procure the teaching and learning materials even though some can be obtained locally or freely.

There are other problems which mentors face in the course of supervising mentees work. These problems are mainly caused by the mentees. Table 6 shows the mentors' responses to the problems they faced when supervising mentees' teaching.

Table 6: Problems mentors faced in the course of supervising mentees work

Problems mentors face	Frequency	Percentage
Mentees' unwillingness to avail themselves for supervision	44	24.4
Mentees' failure to prepare lesson plans	28	15.6
Mentees' absenting themselves from classes without permission	24	13.3
Mentees' unwillingness to accept constructive criticism	84	46.7
Total	180	100

From table 6, it was evident that 46.7% of the mentees are unwilling to accept constructive criticism. Also, 24.4% of the mentors made mention of the unwillingness of the mentees to avail themselves for supervision and 15.6% also reported of failure for the mentees to prepare their lesson plans. These attitudes of the mentees are in contradiction to the educational ethics of the teaching profession. Educational authorities should lay much emphasis on these professional ethics during the orientation for mentees before leaving for their schools of attachment.

Another challenge the researcher unearthed during the observation was that the majority of the mentors did not have in-depth knowledge of subjects like Religious and Moral Education, Physical Education, Music and Dance. This may be so because either they were not part of the curriculum when the mentors were in Training Colleges or the topics they learned in these subjects differed from that of mentees. This situation made mentees not having any proper mentorship in these subjects. It is evident from the

responses that supervisors were not given any incentive and also they lacked the techniques in supervision. This made them not to give their best in the mentoring process.

Research question four: What problems do mentees face in so far as internal supervision is concerned?

This research question was focused on accommodation for mentees availability of teaching and learning materials and preparation of project work and mentees' relationship with mentors among others.

Table 7 presents the mentees' responses on the type of accommodation offered to them during the In-In-Out programme.

Table 7: Type of Accommodation

Type	Frequency	Percentage
Compound	92	30.70%
Self-contained	95	31.70%
Flat	113	37.70%
Total	300	100

From Table 7, 113 mentees representing 37.7% lived in flats, 95 mentees representing 31.7% lived in self-contained houses and 92 mentees representing 30.7% lived in compound houses. Some of the problems associated with compound houses are the sharing of amenities like a place of convenience and bathhouses. There was the problem of overcrowding in some places. At some places, some mentees had no beds and mattresses and had to sleep on the floor at night. Reasons mentees gave for this state of affair was that they had to share a few rooms available because they were secured by college authorities with the help of School Management Committees (SMC). This picture painted above confirms what was stated in the Ghana National Association of Teachers (2003) that provides free accommodation for the mentees could not be sustained because community members could not give up their accommodation forever to new mentees who go out yearly.

Table 8 presents the mentees' responses on the payment for accommodation and utilities.

Table 8: Payment for Accommodation and Utilities

Item	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you pay for accommodation?	8	2.70	292	97.3
Do you pay for utilities?	289	96.30	11	3.7

Majority of the mentees representing 97.3% said they did not pay for accommodation. Only 8 mentees out of the 300 responded that they have been paying for accommodation because they opted to rent their own rooms on health ground. However, the students paid for utilities. This was confirmed by 96.3% of the students.

The landlords agreed to give the accommodation free of charge but the bills of the utilities would be borne by the mentees.

Also, the mentees face a lot of problems when working on their projects. Mentees are still students and as such are required to present a project work as part of the requirement for the award of Diploma in Basic Education Certificate. So even as they are doing the mentorship programme they should be writing their respective project work. Of particular concern was the issue of meeting their supervisors to discuss their project work with them. The mentees could not have the opportunity to meet their supervisors as often as they could. Some students could not get in touch with their supervisors due to transportation problem and their inability to keep to agreed appointments. This made some of them travel on several occasions to the college to consult their supervisors making their project work difficult. This actually affected supervision of instruction because some of the mentees were not easily available for mentors to prepare them for their lessons. Ghana National Association of Teachers (2003) highlighted this problem. The mentees views on whether they enjoy cooperation with their mentors during the In-In-Out or not have been presented in Table 8.

Table 8: You do not enjoy the cooperation of your Mentor

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	31	10.30
Agree	62	20.70
Disagree	63	21.00
Strongly disagree	144	48
Total	300	100

On cooperation of mentors with their mentees, Table 8 indicated that majority of the mentees (48.0%) strongly disagreed to the statement that they do not enjoy the cooperation of their mentors. This means that there is cooperation between the mentors and mentees. This confirms the good interpersonal relationship mentees enjoy from mentors as was observed on the field. These results also confirm the view of Asiedu-Akrofi (1978) that the supervisors' role is to work cooperatively with the teachers to create favourable circumstances for learning in schools.

There were other problems mentees encountered during the practice teaching. The first and notable of them was the issue of financial difficulties. The problem came up during the issues of TLMs and accommodation. Mentees are students who are taken care of by their parents and guardians even though they receive an allowance from the government, they would nonetheless claim that is inadequate. Another problem was inadequate support from the communities where they practiced. They pointed out that there was a problem with water and lack of places of convenience which made life a bit unbearable.

One other problem which confronted mentees and mentors was lack of in-depth knowledge in some subjects like Religious and Moral Education, Physical Education and Music and Dance. Some mentees have not chosen these subjects as their electives. Apart from Holy Child College of Education, where it was observed that 14 mentees

chose Physical Education as their elective subject, the rest lacked the needed competence in the aforementioned subjects. Because the mentors had similar problems, pupils could not receive the appropriate guidance in these subject areas.

Furthermore, mentees said they did not have adequate security. Some of them lose their personal belongings to miscreants in the communities they resided and practiced. A critical example of insecurity happened to some mentees from Holy Child College of Education in 2010 at Ankyeryin Catholic Junior High School and Shama Catholic Primary School respectively; where items such as gas cylinders and cookers, cooking utensils and shoes were stolen whilst they were in school. This could be easily explained as a social menace which can happen to anyone anywhere. Finally, 70% of the mentees complained of overcrowded classes. Most of the classes have large class sizes contrary to the class norms by the Ghana Education Service. They explained that it made teaching and learning not too effective.

Research Question Five: In what ways could the problems be solved?

This research question sought to find out what ways the problems of mentees and mentors could be solved. The areas considered were accommodation and teaching/learning materials for mentees and in-service training for mentors and other solutions respondents felt were applicable.

The biggest problem facing mentees is accommodation. All the 300 mentees craved for more decent accommodation, which they considered if it was provided, could go a long way to make their stay in the place of attachment less burdensome. Mentees have to rent their own accommodation. However, no allowances are given for this purpose. This suggested solution by mentees is validated by what the Ghana National Association of Teachers (2003) stated “to help sustain the programme the issue of free accommodation for the mentees has to be reconsidered. The mentees responses on who should provide teaching and learning materials have been presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Who should provide Teaching and Learning Materials?

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Government	189	60.00
Mentees	23	7.70
Mentors	30	10.00
Government and Mentees	58	19.3
Total	300	100

From Table 9, 63% of mentees were of the view that government should be responsible for the provision of the teaching and learning materials because students are not specifically given any allowance for that and it becomes a burden for them. According to Elliot (2002), teaching and learning materials should be provided by the government, nevertheless, she suggested that teachers should be ready to improvise TLMs to enhance the teaching and learning process. The idea of improvisation of TLMs is in the consonance with views of 7.7% of mentees who felt they should be responsible for providing these materials. They maintained education is a shared responsibility and if

one wants to be perfect in teaching that individual should do all that he/she can to save the situation.

Table 9 further shows that 19.3% of the mentees held the view that the provision of teaching and learning materials should be done by both government and mentees. The government can do this by increasing allowances of teacher-trainees so that they can use part of their allowance to provide the TLMs.

Lastly, 10% of the mentees held the view that the provision of teaching and learning materials should be provided by mentors. They suggested that part of the capitation grant should be used to procure TLMs so that effective teaching and learning can go on. Mentors were asked to indicate the extent to which in-service training was beneficial to them in carrying out the role assigned to them in respect of mentoring teacher-trainees. Their responses confirm that teachers (mentors) need in-service training because of the following reasons:

Teachers have an opportunity to share ideas with others. It enables teachers to learn new things from the supervisors and other related topics to teaching and learning (O'Sullivan, 2001).

Besides the point made by O'Sullivan (2001), in-service training helps teachers learn new trends in teaching techniques because the world is changing rapidly, especially with the introduction of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Some schools use the only ICT in teaching and learning and it is prudent for teachers who are going to be mentors to teacher-trainees to be abreast with the changing world of things (UNESCO, 2001).

The mentors also suggested that incentives should be given in the form of money for transportation and allowance for making TLMs. When they are given incentives, it would motivate them to work assiduously for the success of the out programme. This will help train more teachers for the country.

5. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. The content of training given to supervisors was shallow. It did not equip them enough for their role as supervisors and this adversely affected the supervision of mentees in the teaching and learning process. Thus, for effective supervision of the "In-In-Out programme", there is the need for proper training of mentors to ensure effective teaching and learning.

There were inadequate teaching and learning materials for effective teaching and learning. Consequently, the mentors and mentees could not use a variety of teaching and learning materials, teaching and learning become ineffective and teacher-trainees will not get the full benefit of the mentorship programme.

5.1 Recommendations

It is recommended that various remedial measures should be put in place by those concerned with the teacher education to ensure effective supervisions of the In-In-Out programme. The following recommendations were made:

The Teacher Education Division should employ people with expert knowledge in the supervision of instructions of schools to conduct the in-service training for mentors before the “Out” programme. This will ensure effective supervision of the teacher trainees.

The Principals in the Colleges of Education should increase the period for training for the mentors so that they would acquire all the necessary skills for effective supervision.

To enhance responsibility and willingness on the part of mentors to give the necessary assistance to mentees, there is the need for the government through the teacher education and other stakeholders in education to give them some motivation in the form of allowances.

The government should increase the students’ allowances so that they can use part of their allowances to rent decent accommodation. Also, Religious Bodies and Non-governmental Organizations should help to provide decent accommodation in the various communities for the students on attachment so that they can feel comfortable and prepare adequately for the programme.

Teacher trainees should use part of their allowances to procure more teaching and learning materials for teaching and learning in the schools to supplement that of the headteachers.

The Government, District Assembly and opinion leaders in the various communities where teacher trainees are attached should give allowances to mentors to motivate them to supervise mentees teaching.

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